

CORRELATION AND PATH ANALYSIS STUDIES FOR DROUGHT TOLERANCE IN ADVANCE BREEDING LINES OF SORGHUM [*Sorghum bicolor* (L.) Moench]

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Abstract

With an objective the characters association and direct and indirect effects among grain yield and drought tolerant parameters was carried out by using twenty-six genotypes of rabi sorghum with four checks namely M 35-1, Phule anuradha, Parbhani moti and CSV-29R, these were grown in two replications in randomized block design at Sorghum Research Station, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani during rabi 2023. In current investigation there is existence of higher genotypic correlation when compared to phenotypic correlation this indicates the presence of inherent association among the characters. The correlation coefficient shows the inter relationship between yield and its contributing traits at genotypic and phenotypic levels. Significant and positive association was observed between grain yield per plant and other yield contributing traits like plant height ($G=0.399$, $P=0.394$), panicle length ($G=0.426$, $P=0.389$), fodder yield per plant ($G=0.366$, $P=0.360$), third leaf area ($G=0.450$, $P=0.445$), flag leaf area ($G=0.259$, $P=0.255$) and leaf area index ($G=0.421$, $P=0.390$) at both genotypic and phenotypic levels, this association indicates increase in one or more of these traits results in increase in grain yield. Selection for a trait is effective when both values of correlation and direct effect are higher and positive as this indicates its true association. In this study path analysis revealed presence of positive direct effect on grain yield for traits like days to physiological maturity, panicle length, fodder yield per plant, flag leaf area, leaf area index and harvest index at both genotypic and phenotypic level. Among the thirty genotypes PVR 1501, PVR 1502, PVR 1508, PVR 1516, PVR 1518 and PVR 1523 recorded better performance and these genotypes are considered as the superior genotypes for traits related to yield as well as drought tolerance aspects.

Keywords: Correlation, yield, path analysis, panicle length, drought

Introduction

Sorghum is the fifth most important cereal crop of the world following Rice, Wheat, Maize, and Barley. It is grown as major cereal crop in both *kharif* and *rabi* season for grain and fodder purpose. Sorghum is well known for its versatile use, hardiness, drought tolerance, stability of yield and adaptability over a wide range of soils and climate conditions. Sorghum is unique to adapt to environmental extremes of abiotic and biotic stress. Drought is one of the major abiotic stress results in reduction in yield and crop growth. Identification and understanding the mechanisms of drought tolerance in sorghum have been major goals of breeders and plant physiologists including prolific root system, ability to maintain stomatal opening at low levels of leaf water potential and high osmotic adjustment and various seedling parameters (Ambika *et al.*, 2011). This in turn requires the identification of traits (cost effective and easily measurable) related to terminal drought tolerance (Talwar *et al.*, 2014). Among the various sorghum genotypes, variation to drought tolerance is identified and some of the better adopted genotypes are also identified (Jirali *et al.*, 2007). For stabilizing the production of the crop growing under drought stress during post monsoon especially *rabi* sorghum, identification of the superior traits is essential. In order to study the extent of association between different traits the genotypic and phenotypic simple correlation coefficient were worked out from the respective variances and co-variances. The formula as suggested by Johnson *et al.*, (1955) were used for calculating correlation from the recorded observations. The path coefficient analysis helps in partitioning correlation coefficient into direct and indirect effects across various traits. This would also help in assessing the casual effect relationships and effective selection (Khandelwala *et al.*, 2015). The present study was undertaken with objective to assess characters association studies among grain yield and drought tolerant parameters and direct and indirect effects among grain yield and drought tolerant parameters.

Material and methods

This study comprises of 30 genotypes including four checks namely, M 35-1, Phule anuradha, Parbhani moti and CSV-29R. The genotypes were evaluated in two replications in randomized block design with spacing 45x15 cm and applied with fertilizer dose as 80:40:40 NPK kg/ha at Sorghum Research Station, V.N.M.K.V., Parbhani during *rabi* 2023. The data were recorded for following traits *viz.*, days to 50% flowering, day to physiological maturity, plant height, third leaf area,

flag leaf area, panicle length, panicle width, test weight, fodder yield per plant, harvest index, leaf area index, SCMR at physiological maturity, relative water content and grain yield per plant and used for studying character association and direct and indirect effect on grain yield.

Result and discussion

This investigation is carried out under drought conditions in order to study parameters such as, correlation (association of various characters) and path analysis (direct and indirect effects of various characters on the grain yield) at genotypic and phenotypic levels.

Correlation

Degree of association among various traits can be studied by using one of the important statistical measures called correlation. In present investigation there is existence of higher genotypic correlation when compared to phenotypic correlation this indicates the presence of inherent association among the characters. Studying association among the traits with each other and with yield component plays a major role in crop improvement program as yield is the dependent and complex trait which depends on various component traits. Current investigation was carried out to study correlation coefficient in order to determine the inter relationship between yield and its contributing traits at genotypic and phenotypic levels. Significant and positive association was observed between grain yield per plant and other yield contributing traits like plant height, panicle length, fodder yield per plant, third leaf area, flag leaf area and leaf area index at both genotypic and phenotypic levels, this association indicates increase in one or more of these traits results in increase in grain yield.

Similar results observed by Khandelwal *et al.*, (2015) for panicle length, Jayashree *et al.*, (2015) for flag leaf area and panicle length. Girish *et al.*, (2016) for plant height and fodder yield per plant. Narkhede *et al.*, (2017) for panicle length, fodder yield per plant, El-salam & Hovny (2018) for plant height. More *et al.*, (2019) for plant height, panicle length and fodder yield per plant. Ravali *et al.*, (2021) for third leaf area, flag leaf area and leaf area index.

Generally, the traits which are showing positive and significant correlation with grain yield are given preference as valuable traits for yield improvement. Current study revealed several traits with that type of association; these traits are used in *rabi* sorghum for its improvement of yield.

The only character test weight recorded positive and non-significant association with grain yield per plant at both phenotypic and genotypic level.

Path analysis

Direct and indirect effects of various yield contributing traits cannot be represented by correlation studies. These effects of each trait towards yield component can be obtained by path analysis. Path coefficient analysis was carried out in order to find out the direct and indirect effects of various traits on the grain yield as outlined by the Dewey and Lu (1959).

This analysis creates a decision for grain yield improvement *i.e.*, to carry out the indirect selection for the trait which shows direct effect on the grain yield. Selection for a trait is effective when both the values of correlation and direct effect are higher and positive as this indicates its true association. Simultaneous consideration is made for indirect caused factors for selection if the direct effect is negative or negligible and correlation coefficient is positive. In order to reduce undesirable indirect effect, direct selection for the traits is followed if the direct effect is positive or high and correlation coefficient is negative.

Residual effect plays a major role in deciding how much amount of variability in grain yield *i.e.*, dependent factor is due to causal factors. Moderate or higher residual value indicates besides the trait under study there are several other factors which account for the change in the yield. Present study revealed presence of positive direct effect on grain yield for traits like days to physiological maturity, panicle length, fodder yield per plant, flag leaf area, leaf area index and harvest index at both genotypic and phenotypic level. Results of the current investigation are in agree with Aml A. Tag El-Din *et al.*, (2012) showed that panicle length had positive direct effect on grain yield. Khandelwal *et al.*, (2015) who reported positive direct effect of harvest index on grain yield, Girish *et al.*, (2016) for ear head length, days to maturity, fodder yield per plant. Khadakabhavi & Girish, (2017) who reported existence of positive direct effect of days to physiological maturity on grain yield, Kumar (2017) for panicle length and days to maturity. Assefa *et al.*, (2018) for harvest index. Zinzala *et al.*, (2018) reported positive direct effect for fodder yield per plant and panicle length. Santhiya *et al.*, (2021) for flag leaf area. Chate *et al.*, 2023 were reported positive direct effect of Days to physiological maturity, Panicle length, Fodder yield per plant and harvest index on grain yield. Positive direct effect on grain yield only at genotypic level reported for traits like days to 50% flowering, days to physiological maturity, panicle length, fodder yield per plant, harvest index, flag leaf area and leaf area index. These results are in agree with Narkhede *et al.*, (2017) for panicle length, panicle width, fodder yield per plant. Among all the traits maximum positive direct effect on grain yield recorded for trait fodder yield per plant (0.9021) followed by harvest index (0.6949) while minimum positive direct effect recorded for days to 50% flowering (0.0547) at genotypic level. At phenotypic level maximum positive direct effect on grain yield recorded for trait fodder yield per plant (0.7241) followed by harvest index (0.6355) while minimum positive direct effect recorded for flag leaf area (0.0143).

Among all the traits negative direct effect on grain yield recorded for trait plant height, panicle width, test weight, relative water content, third leaf area and SCMR at physiological maturity at genotypic level. At genotypic level maximum negative direct effect on grain yield recorded for trait SCMR at physiological maturity (-0.4232) while minimum negative direct effect recorded for test weight (-0.0254). At phenotypic level maximum negative direct effect on grain yield recorded for trait SCMR at physiological maturity (-0.2928) while minimum negative direct effect recorded for days to 50% flowering (-0.0013).

Maximum positive indirect effect on grain yield recorded for the trait panicle width (0.4795) and maximum negative indirect effect on grain yield recorded for the trait harvest index (-0.5262) at genotypic level. At phenotypic level maximum positive indirect effect on grain yield recorded for the trait panicle width (0.3210) and maximum negative

indirect effect on grain yield recorded for the trait harvest index (-0.4191).

At genotypic level residual effect among the characters studied was moderate *i.e.*, about 0.5150 and at phenotypic level residual effect was also moderate *i.e.*, about 0.5821. This indicates almost the grain yield is due to the factors studied.

Conclusion

This research project revealed presence of large amount of scope for a breeder in selecting superior genotypes for drought tolerance and yield improvement in *rabi* sorghum as this study recorded significant and positive association of various traits with yield and drought related aspects like plant height, panicle length, fodder yield per plant, third leaf area, flag leaf area and leaf area index.

Generally, the traits which exhibit higher values for genotypic coefficient of variation, phenotypic coefficient of variation, high heritability coupled with high amount of genetic advance and significant and positive correlation with aspects related to yield and drought tolerance are used for identification of superior genotypes for drought tolerance.

Among the thirty genotypes PVR 1501, PVR 1502, PVR 1508, PVR 1516, PVR 1518 and PVR 1523 recorded better performance and these genotypes are considered as the superior genotypes for traits related to yield as well as drought tolerance aspects. Thereby these genotypes can be used for drought tolerance aspects and play a major role in breeding for abiotic stress tolerance *i.e.* for drought and these genotypes can be advanced for further study.

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Table 1 Genotypic Correlation Coefficient for fourteen characters studied in *rabi* sorghum

Characters	Days to 50% flowering	Days to physiological maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle width (cm)	Test wt. (g)	Relative water content (%)	Fodder yield/plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Third leaf area (cm ²)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf area index (%)	SCMR at physiological maturity	Grain yield /plant (g)
Days to 50% flowering	1.000	0.056	-0.328*	-0.005	0.083	-0.266*	0.098	-0.518**	0.297*	-0.402**	-0.437**	-0.305*	0.056	-0.278*
Days to Physiological maturity	0.056	1.000	0.007	-0.191	-0.214	-0.183	-0.019	-0.179	0.189	-0.173	-0.323*	-0.132	0.432**	-0.122
Plant height (cm)	-0.328*	0.007	1.000	0.618**	0.177	0.375**	-0.004	0.294*	-0.105	0.200	0.527**	0.226	-0.162	0.399**
Panicle length (cm)	-0.005	-0.191	0.618**	1.000	0.331**	0.200	0.302*	0.075	0.097	-0.041	0.314*	0.088	-0.056	0.426**
Panicle width (cm)	0.083	-0.214	0.177	0.331**	1.000	-0.047	-0.110	0.532**	-0.136	0.121	0.155	0.330**	0.360**	0.282*
Test wt. (g)	-0.266*	-0.183	0.375**	0.200	-0.047	1.000	-0.376**	0.196	-0.130	0.281*	0.259*	-0.224	-0.325*	0.203
Relative water content (%)	0.098	-0.019	-0.004	0.302*	-0.110	-0.376**	1.000	-0.205	0.263*	-0.130	0.127	0.052	-0.099	-0.050
Fodder yield /plant (g)	-0.518**	-0.179	0.294*	0.075	0.532**	0.196	-0.205	1.000	-0.583**	0.427**	0.356**	0.327*	0.169	0.366**
Harvest index (%)	0.297*	0.189	-0.105	0.097	-0.136	-0.130	0.263*	-0.583**	1.000	-0.014	-0.277*	0.014	-0.064	0.241
Third leaf area (cm ²)	-0.402**	-0.173	0.200	-0.041	0.121	0.281*	-0.130	0.427**	-0.014	1.000	0.524**	0.723**	-0.105	0.450**
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	-0.437**	-0.323*	0.527**	0.314*	0.155	0.259*	0.127	0.356**	-0.277*	0.524**	1.000	0.487**	-0.104	0.259*
leaf area index (%)	-0.305*	-0.132	0.226	0.088	0.330**	-0.224	0.052	0.327*	0.014	0.723**	0.487**	1.000	0.117	0.421**
SCMR at physiological maturity	0.056	0.432**	-0.162	-0.056	0.360**	-0.325*	-0.099	0.169	-0.064	-0.105	-0.104	0.117	1.000	-0.195
Grain yield /plant (g)	-0.278*	-0.122	0.399**	0.426**	0.282*	0.203	-0.050	0.366**	0.241	0.450**	0.259*	0.421**	-0.195	1

*Significant at 5 percent level, ** Significant at 1 percent level.

Table 2 Phenotypic Correlation Coefficient for fourteen characters studied in *rabi sorghum*

Characters	Days to 50% flowering	Days to physiological maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle width (cm)	Test wt. (g)	Relative water content (%)	Fodder yield/plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Third leaf area (cm ²)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf area index (%)	SCMR at physiological maturity	Grain yield /plant (g)
Days to 50% flowering	1.000	0.062	-0.322*	0.011	0.077	-0.235	0.072	-0.504**	0.289*	-0.388**	-0.419**	-0.297*	0.049	-0.263*
Days to Physiological maturity	0.062	1.000	0.011	-0.180	-0.145	-0.158	0.024	-0.158	0.168	-0.159	-0.283*	-0.134	0.312*	-0.101
Plant height (cm)	-0.322*	0.011	1.000	0.567**	0.146	0.351**	-0.001	0.294*	-0.104	0.199	0.524**	0.220	-0.156	0.394**
Panicle length (cm)	0.011	-0.180	0.567**	1.000	0.299*	0.134	0.208	0.071	0.090	-0.043	0.299*	0.059	-0.041	0.389**
Panicle width (cm)	0.077	-0.145	0.146	0.299*	1.000	-0.028	-0.103	0.443**	-0.110	0.107	0.127	0.268*	0.270*	0.231
Test wt. (g)	-0.235	-0.158	0.351**	0.134	-0.028	1.000	-0.268*	0.182	-0.118	0.271*	0.249	-0.178	-0.293*	0.187
Relative water content (%)	0.072	0.024	-0.001	0.208	-0.103	-0.268*	1.000	-0.180	0.232	-0.102	0.118	0.018	-0.064	-0.040
Fodder yield /plant (g)	-0.504**	-0.158	0.294*	0.071	0.443**	0.182	-0.180	1.000	-0.579**	0.426**	0.354**	0.317*	0.162	0.360**
Harvest index (%)	0.289*	0.168	-0.104	0.090	-0.110	-0.118	0.232	-0.579**	1.000	-0.011	-0.274*	0.004	-0.069	0.255*
Third leaf area (cm ²)	-0.388**	-0.159	0.199	-0.043	0.107	0.271*	-0.102	0.426**	-0.011	1.000	0.520**	0.701**	-0.092	0.445**
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	-0.419**	-0.283*	0.524**	0.299*	0.127	0.249	0.118	0.354**	-0.274*	0.520**	1.000	0.474**	-0.108	0.255*
leaf area index (%)	-0.297*	-0.134	0.220	0.059	0.268*	-0.178	0.018	0.317*	0.004	0.701**	0.474**	1.000	0.100	0.390**
SCMR at physiological maturity	0.049	0.312*	-0.156	-0.041	0.270*	-0.293*	-0.064	0.162	-0.069	-0.092	-0.108	0.100	1.000	-0.200
Grain yield /plant (g)	-0.263*	-0.101	0.394**	0.389**	0.231	0.187	-0.040	0.360**	0.255*	0.445**	0.255*	0.390**	-0.200	1

*Significant at 5 percent level, ** Significant at 1 percent level.

Table 3 Direct and indirect effects (genotypic level) of yield components on grain yield

Characters	Days to 50% flowering	Days to physiological maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle width (cm)	Test wt. (g)	Relative water content (%)	Fodder yield/plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Third leaf area (cm ²)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf area index (%)	SCMR at physiological maturity
Days to 50% flowering	0.0547	0.0030	-0.0180	-0.0003	0.0046	-0.0145	0.0054	-0.0283	0.0163	-0.0220	-0.0239	-0.0167	0.0031
Days to Physiological maturity	0.0115	0.2069	0.0015	-0.0395	-0.0442	-0.0379	-0.0039	-0.0370	0.0390	-0.0358	-0.0669	-0.0272	0.0893
Plant height (cm)	0.0935	-0.0020	-0.2848	-0.1761	-0.0505	-0.1067	0.0012	-0.0838	0.0300	-0.0568	-0.1501	-0.0642	0.0462
Panicle length (cm)	-0.0032	-0.1113	0.3604	0.5829	0.1932	0.1168	0.1760	0.0439	0.0565	-0.0242	0.1831	0.0514	-0.0326
Panicle width (cm)	-0.0184	0.0471	-0.0391	-0.0730	-0.2204	0.0103	0.0242	-0.1172	0.0300	-0.0266	-0.0342	-0.0728	-0.0793
Test wt. (g)	0.0068	0.0047	-0.0095	-0.0051	0.0012	-0.0254	0.0096	-0.0050	0.0033	-0.0071	-0.0066	0.0057	0.0082
Relative water content (%)	-0.0360	0.0070	0.0015	-0.1107	0.0403	0.1380	-0.3667	0.0752	-0.0964	0.0475	-0.0465	-0.0190	0.0365
Fodder yield /plant (g)	-0.4676	-0.1612	0.2655	0.0679	0.4795	0.1772	-0.1859	0.9021	-0.5262	0.3852	0.3214	0.2947	0.1521
Harvest index (%)	0.2067	0.1311	-0.0731	0.0677	-0.0945	-0.0905	0.1827	-0.4053	0.6949	-0.0094	-0.1926	0.0095	-0.0447
Third leaf area (cm ²)	0.0801	0.0344	-0.0397	0.0082	-0.0240	-0.0559	0.0258	-0.0850	0.0027	-0.1990	-0.1044	-0.1439	0.0210
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	-0.0662	-0.0489	0.0798	0.0475	0.0235	0.0392	0.0192	0.0539	-0.0419	0.0794	0.1513	0.0736	-0.0158
leaf area index (%)	-0.1159	-0.0499	0.0856	0.0334	0.1254	-0.0851	0.0197	0.1240	0.0052	0.2745	0.1847	0.3796	0.0445
SCMR at physiological maturity	-0.0239	-0.1827	0.0686	0.0236	-0.1523	0.1374	0.0421	-0.0714	0.0272	0.0446	0.0441	-0.0496	-0.4232

Residual effect = 0.5150

Table 4 Direct and indirect effects (phenotypic level) of yield components on grain yield

Characters	Days to 50% flowering	Days to physiological maturity	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Panicle width (cm)	Test wt. (g)	Relative water content (%)	Fodder yield/plant (g)	Harvest index (%)	Third leaf area (cm ²)	Flag leaf area (cm ²)	Leaf area index (%)	SCMR at physiological maturity
Days to 50% flowering	-0.0013	-0.0001	0.0004	0.0000	-0.0001	0.0003	-0.0001	0.0006	-0.0004	0.0005	0.0005	0.0004	-0.0001
Days to Physiological maturity	0.0054	0.0876	0.0010	-0.0158	-0.0127	-0.0138	0.0021	-0.0139	0.0147	-0.0139	-0.0248	-0.0118	0.0273
Plant height (cm)	0.0162	-0.0006	-0.0504	-0.0286	-0.0074	-0.0177	0.0001	-0.0148	0.0053	-0.0100	-0.0264	-0.0111	0.0278
Panicle length (cm)	0.0038	-0.0637	0.2003	0.3533	0.1056	0.0474	0.0734	0.0250	0.0319	-0.0151	0.1058	0.0209	-0.0144
Panicle width (cm)	-0.0082	0.0155	-0.0156	-0.0319	-0.1068	0.0030	0.0110	-0.0473	0.0117	-0.0114	-0.0136	-0.0286	-0.0289
Test wt. (g)	-0.0079	-0.0053	0.0118	0.0045	-0.0009	0.0337	-0.0090	0.0061	-0.0040	0.0091	0.0084	-0.0060	-0.0099
Relative water content (%)	0.0118	-0.0040	0.0002	-0.0341	0.0168	0.0439	-0.1638	0.0295	-0.0380	0.0167	-0.0193	-0.0029	0.0105
Fodder yield /plant (g)	-0.3647	-0.1148	0.2129	0.0511	0.3210	0.1318	-0.1303	0.7241	-0.4191	0.3084	0.2563	0.2293	0.1172
Harvest index (%)	0.1838	0.1065	-0.0664	0.0574	-0.0697	-0.0750	0.1475	-0.3678	0.6355	-0.0067	-0.1744	0.0025	-0.0437
Third leaf area (cm ²)	0.0163	0.0067	-0.0084	0.0018	-0.0045	-0.0114	0.0043	-0.0179	0.0004	-0.0421	-0.0219	-0.0295	0.0039
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	-0.0060	-0.0040	0.0075	0.0043	0.0018	0.0036	0.0017	0.0051	-0.0039	0.0074	0.0143	0.0068	-0.0015
leaf area index (%)	-0.0742	-0.0335	0.0548	0.0148	0.0670	-0.0444	0.0044	0.0791	0.0010	0.1750	0.1183	0.2497	0.0249
SCMR at physiological maturity	-0.0142	-0.0913	0.0456	0.0119	-0.0792	0.0859	0.0188	-0.0474	0.0202	0.0270	0.0316	-0.0292	-0.2928

Residual effect = 0.5821